

Often people that own bronze, zinc or other metal sculptures and other works of art, want to clean up and polish their piece at home rather than have it done by a professional. This is perfectly fine as long as the utmost care and consideration is taken. What most people do not realize is that many commercial waxes can produce an acid that can cause damage to their piece.

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Generally speaking it is recommended to keep most sculptures waxed, particularly if they are displayed outdoors. Raw metal reacts with moisture, air and anything else it comes in contact with such as pollutants in the air or acids in human skin. Extreme direct sunlight can also play a big part in metal damage on outdoor pieces. The right wax provides a protective layer between the metal and damaging elements.

It is a common belief that beeswax and carnauba wax are good waxes for metals. The truth is that these waxes can actually produce acid when oxidation and hydrolysis occur and result in damage to metal and acid-sensitive materials. A best choice is a wax that is chemically neutral, free of damaging acids. One product that is used by many restoration and conservation professionals is called Renaissance wax. It was created in the 1950's in Britain under the directive of international conservationists that understood the problems caused by traditional waxes. The product that resulted removes residues, polishes, buffs to a hard finish, remains clear after multiple applications and is safe for many different materials. It is expensive but only a small amount is needed and recommended. There may be other similar products on the market, but this one is the original and has been used in numerous high-profile museums and galleries and has been recommended by highly reputable [powerful metal detector](#) sources. Always remember to use sparingly and only work small areas at a time.

Restoration professionals often create their own waxes and this may be an additional source for the sculpture owner wanting to protect their piece. Professionals can customize a wax for a particular project by adding pigments to enhance or blend certain areas on a sculpture. Patinas are in a constant state of change and if properly maintained, the slight changes are most always on the enrichment side.

Once waxed, a metal sculpture is protected - but for how long? If it is in a very temperature and light regulated, dust-free environment it will be good for many years. If it is exposed to elements, particularly direct sunlight, ocean air or polluted air, cleaning and waxing should be repeated more often - possibly every year or even more often in some cases. The important thing is to prevent damage before it occurs and of course - using the right wax to truly protect and not cause new problems.

Metal Detector Reviews Are Beneficial

Metal detector reviews will help you find the best detector to fit your needs. Metal detector reviews will help you check out reliability of particular manufacturers, makes, and models. You should look at several different metal detector reviews prior to buying, to ensure you find a detector that will do all that you need it do, want it to do, all at a reasonable price.

What Will I Find In Such A Review?

Alerts: Detectors have an audio signal or beep, but by reading a review you will find out if the detector has a vibrating option, or a variety of tones to let you know the different types of metal you are detecting.

Depth: Metal detector reviews will let you know how far down (depth) the detector can sense metal. By reading metal detector reviews, you will find that some detectors can detect any metal object as deep as 12 inches, while some can not only detect, but also tell exact depth location.

Detection Mode: The metal detector reviews will also tell you information regarding detection modes. Usually

there are detectors that have four different modes. These modes are relics (bullets, buttons, etc.); prospecting; coins; and jewelry. The metal detector reviews will let you know if you are able to use one of these modes alone, or if you can use two modes at the same time. If you use a single mode, you will have better success (or better chances) of finding what you set out to find.

Ground balance: Did you know the ground contains metal that occurs naturally in its soil? Detectors can tell you how sophisticated the detector is to find and cancel out those natural types of metals. The better makes and models of detectors will be able to tell you the exact types of metals you are looking for as you find them.

Battery life: Detectors will usually run on AA batteries, which will usually last approximately 20-30 hours.

Sensitivity: Metal detector reviews will be able to measure which makes and models have the best adjustable sensitivity ratings. This is an important factor when detecting, so you can distinguish between ground metals and your hidden treasures.

Display: Another topic metal detector reviews will cover is display. The display on detectors will vary from simple measures to complicated measures. Take a look at the models you are looking at to see what they have to offer in display.

Where Can I Find Good Reviews?

There are online sites offering reviews on metal detectors, makes, and models. Look at more than one site and review before making your final purchasing decision. Reviews are mostly opinions, so get a wide range to help you make your choice. You will be able to make an educated decision on your own, and have confidence it was the right one.